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Teaching Strategies in Social Studies and Academic Performance in Dapitan City National High School: Basis for Intervention Program

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ABSTRACT: This study aimed to determine the teaching strategies in Social Studies and students' academic performance at Dapitan City National High School, Schools Division of Dapitan City, during School Year 2025–2026. It involved 293 junior high school student-respondents whose accomplished questionnaires were considered valid for analysis. The study employed a survey descriptive-correlational research design using a structured questionnaire checklist and students' actual academic performance records. Weighted mean, standard deviation, and Spearman rank-order correlation were used in the analysis of data through Microsoft Excel Data Analysis ToolPak and Jamovi. Findings revealed that the respondents perceived the Social Studies teaching strategies as practiced to a full extent, with an overall AWV of 4.38 and SD of 0.534. Their academic performance was rated outstanding, with an AWV of 4.54 and SD of 0.499. A significant positive relationship was found between Social Studies teaching strategies and academic performance, with a correlation coefficient of 0.394 and a p-value of $< .001$. The study concludes that effective teaching strategies in Social Studies are associated with better academic performance among learners. Based on the findings, it is recommended that DepEd officials strengthen teacher training and curriculum support programs, school heads intensify instructional supervision and mentoring, Social Studies teachers continue using varied and learner-centered strategies, parents support learners' study habits at home, students actively participate in class activities, and future researchers conduct related studies in other school settings.

KEYWORDS: Social Studies, teaching strategies, academic performance, role playing, cooperative learning, intervention program.

INTRODUCTION

Teaching strategies refer to the planned methods, techniques, and classroom practices used by teachers to facilitate learning, improve understanding, and encourage students' active participation in lessons. In Social Studies, effective teaching strategies are important because they help learners analyze social issues, connect lessons to real-life situations, and develop critical thinking, collaboration, and civic awareness. Darling-Hammond et al. (2020), meaningful and supportive teaching practices improve students' learning because they respond to learners' developmental needs and promote deeper academic engagement. Similarly, Tatal and Yazar (2023) found that active learning strategies improve students' academic achievement and retention, especially when learners are given opportunities to participate, discuss, collaborate, and apply concepts in meaningful activities. Teaching strategies are essential in making classroom instruction more engaging, learner-centered, and effective in improving students' academic performance.

Social Studies is an important subject in basic education because it helps learners understand society, culture, history, governance, citizenship, and real-life social issues. It develops not only academic knowledge but also critical thinking, decision-making, civic responsibility, respect for diversity, and active participation in the community. According to Shih (2024), Social Studies education helps learners become aware of community life, cultural diversity, global concerns, and sustainability issues, making the subject essential in developing responsible and socially aware citizens. Similarly, Mellado-Moreno and Burgos (2025) emphasized that Social Studies plays a vital role in preparing learners for global citizenship because it equips them with the knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes needed to participate meaningfully in democratic and social life. These studies suggest that Social Studies is not limited to classroom learning, but also serves as a foundation for forming informed, reflective, and responsible individuals.

Closely linked to the quality of instruction is academic performance, which refer to the extents to which learners achieve the desired competencies, skills and learning outcomes as measured through grades, assessments, and classroom outputs. In Social Studies, higher academic performance reflects a students' ability to understand historical events, analyze social phenomena, explain democratic processes, and apply civic values to actual situations. Darling-Hammond et.al (2020) stressed that students learn best when instruction is meaningful, organized, and developmentally responsive. Likewise, Tatal and Yazar (2023) found that active learning strategies significantly improve academic achievement

and long-term retention. This implies that academic success is not solely dependent on the student's ability but is heavily influenced by how well the teacher designs instruction and creates opportunities for meaningful engagement.

The effectiveness of teaching strategies directly impacts how students perform and progress in their studies. Research indicates that instructional methods act as a significant predictor of student achievement, determining whether learners remain motivated or become disengaged. In the Philippine setting, Agustin et.al (2025) found that teaching strategies in Social Studies are strongly associated with academic performance, suggesting that instruction does not occur in isolation directly influences how students process and retain information. Similarly, Lamaro and Anena (2024) reported that dynamic approaches such as group work, role playing, and project-based learning yields better results compared to traditional lecture methods. These findings confirm that when teachers utilize varied, interactive, and well-structured strategies, students are more likely to participate actively, understand lessons deeply, and achieve higher grades.

Social Studies is fundamentally designed to help learners understand the world around them and their role in society. It integrates knowledge from history, geography, economics, and political science to develop a holistic view of human life and community. Consequently, the way this subject is taught plays a significant role in whether the students appreciate its relevance or view it as merely a requirement for promotion. Zhang et.al (2024) highlighted that effective teaching strategies greatly influence students' motivation and engagement. Therefore, evaluating how teaching is conducted in the classroom is necessary to ensure that the subject fulfill its purpose not only for academic excellence but also for character building and civic consciousness.

Despite the wealth of information available in educational literature, there remains noticeable gap in context-specific research, particularly within Dapitan City National High School. Most existing studies focus on general education or are conducted in different regions and settings, leaving the specific status of Social Studies instruction in this school largely underexplored. This limitation is critical, especially since Social Studies is the primary venue where students discuss pressing national issues – such as governance, accountability, and public responsibility. Without local data, school administrators and teachers lack an empirical basis to determine if current strategies are effectively helping students connect lessons to reality while maintaining high academic standards.

Moreover, there is a need to apply which specific strategies are most effective and which areas may require improvement. While many studies confirm the positive relationship between teaching methods and performance, there is still limited information on how these variables specifically interact in the local context of Dapitan City. Addressing this gap is important to ensure that instructional practices are evidence-based and responsive to the needs of the learners. Therefore, this study is deemed necessary to assess the extent of teaching strategies employed in Social Studies and determine their relationship to students' academic performance. The findings of this research will serve as a solid foundation and basis for crafting a localized intervention program aimed at enhancing instructional delivery, strengthening civic literacy, and ultimately improving student learning outcomes at Dapitan City National High School.

LITERATURE

Teaching Strategies in Social Studies

Teaching strategies in Social Studies refer to the planned methods and classroom approaches teachers use to help learners understand social, historical, political, economic, and cultural concepts. These strategies are important because Social Studies is not limited to memorization of facts; it also develops critical thinking, civic awareness, decision-making, and social understanding among learners. Bihag et al. (2025) emphasized that Social Studies teachers use instructional practices that shape how students participate in class and respond to academic tasks, showing that teaching strategies are central to classroom effectiveness. In the same way, Kyei et al. (2025) explained that both teacher-centered and learner-centered strategies in Social Studies can support knowledge construction when they are properly aligned with the goals of instruction.

Lecture-Discussion Method

The lecture-discussion method is widely recognized as a structured teaching strategy in which the teacher first presents the lesson systematically and then engages learners in questioning, clarification, and guided discussion. This method remains relevant because it combines the strengths of direct instruction and student interaction, allowing teachers to explain difficult concepts while also encouraging learners to process ideas more actively. Hafeez (2021) found that teaching methods significantly affect students' academic achievement and interest, showing that classroom strategies shape how well learners understand lessons and respond to instruction. In a related discussion, Agustin et al. (2025) explained that instructional practices in Social Studies influence students' academic performance through classroom learning processes, suggesting that organized teacher-led strategies such as lecture-discussion continue to play an important role in student learning.

Cooperative Learning

Cooperative learning is a student-centered teaching strategy in which learners work together in small groups to achieve common academic goals, solve problems, and construct understanding through interaction. This strategy is widely recognized for promoting active participation, shared responsibility, and deeper processing of lesson content. Al-Mubireek (2021) found that cooperative learning produced better student achievement than traditional teaching, emphasizing that structured peer interaction can improve both academic and social outcomes. In a broader synthesis, Boke et al. (2025) reported a significantly positive overall effect of cooperative learning on students' learning outcomes, showing that the strategy supports cognitive, affective, and social development across learning settings. These findings suggest that cooperative learning remains an effective instructional approach for improving classroom performance and participation.

Incorporating Technology and Multimedia Resources

Incorporating technology and multimedia resources has become an important teaching strategy because it allows teachers to present lessons through videos, presentations, images, audio materials, online platforms, and interactive digital tools that can make learning more engaging and understandable. In Social Studies, these resources are especially useful because they help learners visualize historical events, social issues, places, and cultural realities that may be difficult to explain through verbal instruction alone. Jibililu (2024) emphasized that instructional materials significantly influence Social Studies learning outcomes, noting that well-selected materials improve students' understanding and overall

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classroom learning. Similarly, Bihag et al. (2025) found that Social Studies teachers’ instructional practices, including the use of varied resources, shape student participation and academic performance, suggesting that technology-supported instruction can strengthen the delivery of lessons and students’ responsiveness in class.

Role Playing

Role playing is an active teaching strategy in which students assume characters, situations, or social positions to explore ideas and issues in a more concrete and participatory way. In classroom instruction, this approach helps learners move beyond passive listening by allowing them to experience concepts through action, dialogue, and interaction. Brown (2023) described role play as an effective and enduring active teaching strategy that keeps students engaged because it encourages interaction, clear objectives, and purposeful participation. In a more recent classroom-based study, Löfstrand et al. (2025) found that role-playing exercises supported both cognitive and emotional engagement when students dealt with complex social phenomena such as stereotyping, conformity, and racism. These findings suggest that role playing is valuable because it strengthens understanding while making learning more meaningful and experiential.

Students’ Academic Performance

Students’ academic performance refers to the level of achievement learners attain in school as reflected in grades, test results, classroom outputs, and other indicators of learning outcomes. It is widely regarded as an important measure of how well students are able to understand lessons, develop competencies, and meet curricular expectations. Cai et al. (2025) explained that academic performance is shaped by both internal and external factors, particularly students’ resilience and teacher support, showing that achievement is not only a result of ability but also of learning conditions and guidance. In another study, Delgado-Galindo et al. (2025) emphasized that a positive school climate is crucial in improving students’ academic performance because it creates better learning opportunities and supports the quality of daily schoolwork. These findings suggest that academic performance is influenced by a combination of personal, instructional, and environmental factors.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework is illustrated in Figure 1. Part I depicts the independent variable, which is the Teaching Strategies in Social Studies. This variable is measured using four key indicators: (1) Lecture -Discussion Method; (2) Cooperative Learning; (3) Incorporation of Technology and Multimedia Resources; and (4) Role Playing. This section consists of forty (40) items designed to assess the extent to which strategies are employed by teachers. Part II illustrate the dependent variable, which is the Students’ Academic Performance. This is evaluated and measured based on the learners’ performance ratings following the standard grading system adopted by the Department of Education (DepEd).

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine the teaching strategies in social studies and students’ academic performance in Dapitan City National High School, during the the school year 2025-2026.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the respondents' perceived level of teaching strategies in Social Studies in terms of:
 - 2.1 lecture discussion method;
 - 2.2 cooperative learning; and
 - 2.3 incorporating technology and multimedia resources; and
 - 2.4 role playing?
2. What is the respondents’ level of academic performance?

3. Is there a significant relationship between the perceived level of teaching strategies in social studies and respondents’ level academic performance?

Hypothesis

3. There is no significant relationship between perceived level of teaching strategies in social studies and respondents’ level academic performance.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study is limited to examining the teaching strategies in Social Studies and their relationship to the academic performance of two hundred ninety-three (293) junior high school at Dapitan City National High School, Schools Division of Dapitan City, during the School Year 2025–2026. The study focused on four key indicators of teaching strategies: the lecture-discussion method, cooperative learning, the incorporation of technology and multimedia resources, and role-playing. These indicators were assessed using a structured research instrument consisting of

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forty (40) items and served as the components of the independent variable, representing the instructional practices that may influence students' learning outcomes. Meanwhile, the dependent variable, academic performance, was measured using the respondents' official grades in Social Studies for School Year 2025–2026, as certified and provided by their respective class advisers. This procedure ensured that the academic performance data were accurate, reliable, and based on the students' actual school records.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Method Used

The study utilized survey and descriptive-correlational research methods. The researcher utilized the survey method to collect data on the teaching strategies in Social Studies and academic performance through a questionnaire. According to Check and Schutt (2017), describe survey research as “a systematic method of collecting information from a sample of individuals through the use of questionnaires or interviews to measure attitudes, beliefs, behaviors, and characteristics.” They emphasize that surveys allow researchers to gather large amounts of data efficiently and are often used alongside experiments and observational methods to validate findings.” Creswell and Guetterman (2019), define correlational research as the systematic investigation of relationships among two or more variables, conducted without any experimental manipulation of those variables. Correlational research is a non-experimental approach in which a researcher quantifies variables and assesses the statistical relationship between the teaching strategies in Social Studies and academic performance, without the influence of extraneous variables.

Research Instrument

The questionnaire used in the study consisted of three parts: Part I: teaching strategies in Social Studies and academic performance adopted from Agustin et al. (2025), with four indicators, namely: lecture discussion method; cooperative learning; incorporating technology and multimedia resources; and role playing; Part II: Students Academic Performance is the actual performance of students taken from class advisers.

Ethical Consideration

This study secured approval from the Research and Ethics Committee of the Department of Education before the conduct of data gathering. Informed consent was obtained from the institution and the individual respondents prior to their participation. The questionnaire was written in clear and understandable language to ensure voluntary and informed participation. The identities of the respondents were kept anonymous, and all information gathered was treated with strict confidentiality. Only essential research data were retained for academic and future research purposes.

Statistical Treatment of the Data

Presented below are the statistical tools utilized in the treatment and analysis of the data gathered.

Weighted Mean. This is used to quantify the respondents' ratings on the teaching strategies in Social Studies and academic performance.

Scoring Procedure

Teaching Strategies in Social Studies			
Scale	Range of Values	Description	Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Full Extent
4	3.41-4.20	Agree	Great Extent
3	2.61-3.40	Somewhat Agree	Considerable Extent
2	1.81-2.60	Disagree	Some Extent
1	1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree	Lesser Extent

ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE (Based on DepEd Order no. 8 Series of 2015)		
Scale	Description	Grading Scale
5	Outstanding	90 – 100
4	Very Satisfactory	85 – 89
3	Satisfactory	80 – 84
2	Fair Satisfactory	75 – 79
1	Did Not Meet Expectation	Below 75

Standard Deviation. This is used to determine the homogeneity and heterogeneity of the respondents' score, where $SD \leq 3$ is homogenous and $SD > 3$ is heterogeneous Aiken & Susane (2001); Refugio et al. (2019).

Spearman Rank-Order Correlation Coefficient (Spearman rho). This is used to determine the correlation between teaching strategies in Social Studies and academic performance. The following guide in interpreting the correlation value proposed by Cohen et al. (2014) was utilized in this study:

Value	Size	Interpretation
± 0.50 to ± 1.00	Large	High positive/negative correlation
± 0.30 to $\pm .49$	Medium	Moderate positive/negative correlation
± 0.10 to ± 0.29	Small	Low positive/negative correlation
± 0.01 to ± 0.09	Negligible	Slight positive/negative correlation
No correlation		

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

The data are presented following the statement of the problems of the current study. The study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the respondents' perceived level of teaching strategies in Social Studies in terms of:
 - 2.1 lecture discussion method;
 - 2.2 cooperative learning; and
 - 2.3 incorporating technology and multimedia resources; and
 - 2.4 role playing?

Table 1: Respondents' perceived level of teaching strategies in Social Studies in terms of Lecture discussion method.

Statements	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. My teacher effectively delivers content through lectures.	4.59	0.680	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
2. My teacher's lectures help me understand complex topics.	4.46	0.723	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
3. My teacher's lectures keep me engaged throughout the class.	4.26	0.881	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
4. My teacher's lectures encourage critical thinking.	4.34	0.736	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
5. My teacher's allows for interaction and questions during lectures.	4.35	0.873	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
6. My teacher provides clear explanations during lectures.	4.49	0.720	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
7. My teacher's lectures support my learning style.	4.33	0.849	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
8. My teacher effectively covers the course material through lectures.	4.17	0.871	Agree	Great Extent
9. My teacher's lectures encourage note-taking and active listening.	4.39	0.818	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
10. My teacher's lectures help me retain information.	4.33	0.866	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
Overall	4.37	0.583	Strongly Agree	Full Extent

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

Table 1 presents the respondents' perceived level of teaching strategies in terms of the lecture-discussion method. The findings reveal an overall Average Weighted Value (AWV) of 4.37 with a Standard Deviation of 0.583, which described as "Strongly Agree" and interpreted as practiced to a Full Extent. Among the specific indicators, the statement, "My teacher effectively delivers content through lectures," obtained the highest rating (AWV= 4.59), followed by "My teacher provides clear explanations" (AWV= 4.49) and "My teacher helps me understand complex topics" (AWV=4.46). On the other hand, the lowest rating was on "My teacher effectively covers the course material" (AWV= 4.17), which was still interpreted as practiced to a Great extent. This means that the respondents perceived their teachers as highly competent in using the lecture-discussion strategy. The teachers are effective in presenting lessons clearly, encouraging interaction, and guiding students to understand Social Studies concepts. However, the slightly lower rating on covering materials suggest that there may still be room for improvement in terms of lesson pacing, organization, and time management. This implies that while the lecture discussion methods remain effective and relevant, teachers should continuously enrich it by integrating visual aids, real-life examples, and guided note-taking activities. Strengthening this strategy ensures that learners remain engaged, attentive, and capable of retaining information necessary for good academic performance.

The current finding is supported by Altaftazani et al. (2025), who found that lecture-discussion methods are widely used and effective in Social Studies when delivered properly. Similarly, Tatal and Yazar (2023) emphasized that lecture-based instruction becomes more powerful when combined with active participation, questioning, and meaningful discussion, leading to better achievement and long-term retention.

Table 2: Respondents' perceived level of teaching strategies in Social Studies in terms of Cooperative Learning.

Statements	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. My teacher effectively implements cooperative learning activities.	4.40	0.791	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
2. Cooperative learning activities organized by my teacher enhance my understanding of the subject matter.	4.37	0.816	Strongly Agree	Full Extent

3. My teacher encourages teamwork and collaboration during cooperative learning activities.	4.43	0.848	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
4. My teacher fosters a sense of community in the classroom through cooperative learning.	4.37	0.860	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
5. My teacher's use cooperative learning from my peers.	4.17	0.982	Agree	Great Extent
6. Cooperative learning activities organized by my teacher improve my communication skills.	4.55	0.732	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
7. My teacher allows for diverse perspectives to be shared during cooperative learning.	4.40	0.772	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
8. My teacher's use of cooperative learning encourages problem-solving skills.	4.45	0.787	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
9. Cooperative learning activities organized by my teacher increase my engagement in class.	4.40	0.794	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
10. My teacher makes cooperative learning activities enjoyable and beneficial.	4.38	0.813	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
Overall	4.39	0.585	Strongly Agree	Full Extent

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

Table 2 presents the respondents' perceived level of teaching strategies in Social Studies in terms of cooperative learning. The findings show that cooperative learning obtained an overall AWV of 4.39 and SD of 0.585, described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as practiced to a Full Extent. Among the statements, the highest mean was on "Cooperative learning activities organized by my teacher improve my communication skills," with an AWV of 4.55 and SD of 0.732, interpreted as Full Extent. This was followed by "My teacher's use of cooperative learning encourages problem-solving skills," with an AWV of 4.45 and SD of 0.787, and "My teacher encourages teamwork and collaboration during cooperative learning activities," with an AWV of 4.43 and SD of 0.848, both interpreted as Full Extent. Meanwhile, the lowest mean was on "My teacher's use cooperative learning from my peers," with an AWV of 4.17 and SD of 0.982, described as Agree and interpreted as Great Extent. Although it received the lowest rating, it still reflects a positive perception of the strategy. This means that the respondents perceived cooperative learning as an effective teaching strategy that promotes communication, teamwork, collaboration, problem-solving, sharing of diverse perspectives, and classroom engagement. The overall result suggests that students recognized the value of working with classmates in understanding Social Studies concepts and participating actively in class activities. This implies that Social Studies teachers may continue strengthening cooperative learning activities in the classroom. Since Social Studies involves civic issues, culture, history, geography, and social interaction, cooperative learning may help learners discuss ideas, listen to others, develop respect for different perspectives, and connect lessons to real-life situations. Teachers may further improve this strategy by assigning clear group roles, providing structured tasks, utilizing peer evaluation, using guided discussion questions, and requiring performance-based outputs to ensure that all learners participate meaningfully.

The current finding is supported by Valente, Lourenço, and Németh (2020), who emphasized that cooperative learning helps develop students' social and communication skills through structured peer interaction. Similarly, Gillies (2016) explained that cooperative learning promotes active engagement, positive interdependence, and deeper understanding because students work together to accomplish shared learning goals.

Table 3: Respondents' perceived level of teaching strategies in Social Studies in terms of Incorporating Technology and Multimedia Resources.

Statements	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. My teacher effectively integrates technology into lessons.	4.33	0.808	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
2. Multimedia resources used by my teacher help me visualize abstract concepts.	4.35	0.728	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
3. My teacher's integration of technology makes lessons more interactive.	4.33	0.770	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
4. Multimedia resources used by my teacher cater to different learning styles.	4.43	2.352	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
5. Technology integrated by my teacher enhances my ability to grasp complex topics.	4.31	0.861	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
6. Multimedia resources used by my teacher learning more engaging.	4.34	0.836	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
7. My teacher's integration of make technology improves my retention of information.	4.31	0.838	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
8. Multimedia resources used by my teacher provide opportunities for self-paced learning.	4.32	0.816	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
9. My teacher effectively uses technology to make learning materials accessible.	4.30	0.854	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
10. Multimedia resources used by my teacher enrich classroom discussions.	4.29	0.862	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
Overall	4.33	0.634	Strongly Agree	Full Extent

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

Table 3 presents the respondents' perceived level of teaching strategies in Social Studies in terms of incorporating technology and multimedia resources. The findings show that this teaching strategy obtained an overall AWV of 4.33 and SD of 0.634, described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as practiced to a Full Extent. Among the statements, the highest mean was on "Multimedia resources used by my teacher cater to different learning styles," with an AWV of 4.43 and SD of 2.352, interpreted as Full Extent. This was followed by "Multimedia resources used by my teacher help me visualize abstract concepts," with an AWV of 4.35 and SD of 0.728, and "Multimedia resources used by my teacher make learning more engaging," with an AWV of 4.34 and SD of 0.836, both interpreted as Full Extent. Meanwhile, the lowest mean was on "Multimedia resources used by my teacher enrich classroom discussions," with an AWV of 4.29 and SD of 0.862, although it was still described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Full Extent. This means that the respondents perceived their Social Studies teachers as effectively using technology and multimedia resources to support learning. The results suggest that multimedia materials help learners visualize abstract ideas, understand complex topics, improve retention, access learning materials, and engage more actively in classroom discussions. The overall rating indicates that technology integration is highly evident in Social Studies instruction. This implies that Social Studies teachers should continue integrating technology and multimedia resources in classroom teaching. Since Social Studies includes historical events, geographical locations, civic issues, cultural practices, and social realities, the use of videos, digital maps, presentations, images, online resources, and interactive materials may make lessons clearer, more engaging, and more meaningful to learners. However, teachers may also strengthen the use of multimedia resources for discussion-based learning by allowing learners to analyze videos, interpret digital maps, evaluate online sources, and connect multimedia content to real-life social issues.

The current finding is supported by Schmid et al. (2023), who emphasized that digital technology can improve student learning when it is meaningfully integrated into instruction rather than used only as a presentation tool. Similarly, Haleem et al. (2022) explained that digital technologies in education support interactive learning, improve access to instructional materials, and help learners understand concepts through visual and multimedia formats.

Table 4: Respondents' perceived level of teaching strategies in Social Studies in terms of Role Playing.

Statements	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. My teacher effectively incorporates activities into lessons.	4.49	0.830	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
2. Role-playing activities into organized by my teacher help me understand historical events better.	4.49	0.720	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
3. My teacher's use of role-playing activities makes learning social studies more enjoyable.	4.48	0.747	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
4. Role-playing activities organized by my teacher encourage empathy and perspective-taking.	4.40	0.750	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
5. My teacher's use of role-playing activities enhances my critical thinking skills.	4.40	0.786	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
6. Role-playing activities organized by my teacher improve my communication skills.	4.40	0.820	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
7. My teacher allows me to actively participate in learning through role-playing activities.	4.41	0.791	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
8. Role-playing activities organized by my teacher make learning relevant and practical.	4.41	0.812	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
9. My teacher's use of role-playing activities fosters creativity and imagination.	4.31	0.854	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
10. Role-playing activities organized by my teacher make complex concepts more relatable.	4.48	0.792	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
Overall	4.43	0.585	Strongly Agree	Full Extent

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

Table 4 presents the respondents' perceived level of teaching strategies in Social Studies in terms of role playing. The findings show that role playing obtained an overall AWV of 4.43 and SD of 0.585, described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as practiced to a Full Extent. Among the statements, the highest means were on "My teacher effectively incorporates activities into lessons" and "Role-playing activities organized by my teacher help me understand historical events better," both with an AWV of 4.49, interpreted as Full Extent. These were followed by "My teacher's use of role-playing activities makes learning Social Studies more enjoyable" and "Role-playing activities organized by my teacher make complex concepts more relatable," both with an AWV of 4.48, also interpreted as Full Extent. Meanwhile, the lowest mean was on "My teacher's use of role-playing activities fosters creativity and imagination," with an AWV of 4.31 and SD of 0.854, but it was still described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Full Extent. This means that the respondents perceived role playing as a highly evident and effective teaching strategy in Social Studies. The results suggest that role-playing activities help learners understand historical events, make lessons enjoyable, encourage empathy and perspective-taking, enhance critical thinking and communication skills, and make complex concepts more relatable. This implies that Social Studies teachers may continue using role playing as an interactive and experiential strategy. Since Social Studies deals with historical events, civic issues, cultural experiences, and social realities, role playing may help students place themselves in real-life or historical situations, understand different perspectives, and develop deeper appreciation of the lesson. Teachers may further improve this strategy by giving

clear roles, structured scenarios, reflection questions, and post-activity discussions to strengthen students' creativity, analysis, and connection of the activity to academic learning.

The current finding is supported by Mastul (2023), who found that the role-playing method had a significant effect on students' learning outcomes in Social Studies, with students exposed to role playing obtaining higher learning outcomes than those taught through ordinary lecture methods. Similarly, Rashid and Qaisar (2017) emphasized that role play is a productive teaching strategy for developing students' critical thinking because it allows learners to actively engage with situations, analyze roles, and express ideas through performance-based learning.

Table 5: Summary of respondents' perceived level of teaching strategies in Social Studies.

Statements	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Lecture Discussion Method.	4.37	0.583	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
2. Cooperative Learning	4.39	0.585	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
3. Incorporating Technology and Multimedia Resources	4.33	0.634	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
4. Role Playing.	4.43	0.585	Strongly Agree	Full Extent
Overall	4.38	0.534	Strongly Agree	Full Extent

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

Table 5 presents the summary of the respondents' perceived level of teaching strategies in Social Studies. The findings show that the overall rating obtained an AWV of 4.38 and SD of 0.534, described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as practiced to a Full Extent. Among the four teaching strategies, Role Playing obtained the highest mean, with an AWV of 4.43 and SD of 0.585, followed by Cooperative Learning with an AWV of 4.39 and SD of 0.585. The Lecture Discussion Method ranked third with an AWV of 4.37 and SD of 0.583, while Incorporating Technology and Multimedia Resources obtained the lowest mean, with an AWV of 4.33 and SD of 0.634. Although it had the lowest mean, it was still described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as practiced to a Full Extent. This means that the respondents perceived Social Studies teachers as highly utilizing various teaching strategies, particularly role playing, cooperative learning, lecture discussion, and technology-supported instruction. The result suggests that Social Studies instruction in Dapitan City National High School is not limited to one method but uses varied approaches that promote participation, collaboration, communication, visualization, and understanding of Social Studies concepts. This implies that Social Studies teachers should continue applying varied and learner-centered teaching strategies to sustain students' interest and academic engagement. Since role playing obtained the highest mean, teachers may further use simulation, dramatization, historical reenactment, and perspective-taking activities to make Social Studies lessons more meaningful and relatable. However, since incorporating technology and multimedia resources obtained the lowest mean, teachers may also strengthen the use of digital maps, videos, presentations, online resources, and interactive materials to enrich classroom discussion and improve learners' understanding of historical, civic, geographical, and cultural topics.

The current finding is supported by Mastul (2023), who found that students exposed to role-playing methods in Social Studies obtained higher learning outcomes than those taught through ordinary lecture methods, showing that role playing can make Social Studies learning more engaging and meaningful. Similarly, recent Social Studies research on instructional practices and academic performance highlights that teaching strategies are important in supporting Grade 10 learners' academic achievement in Social Studies. Moreover, the National Council for the Social Studies emphasizes that technology should be connected with meaningful Social Studies content and skills rather than used merely as a tool, which supports the need to strengthen multimedia integration in classroom instruction.

2. What is the respondents' level of academic performance?

Table 6: Respondents' perceived level of teaching strategies in Academic Performance.

Statements	AWV	SD	Description
Academic Performance	4.54	0.499	Outstanding

Table 6 presents the respondents' perceived level of academic performance. The finding shows that academic performance obtained an AWV of 4.54 and SD of 0.499, described as Outstanding. This indicates that the respondents demonstrated a very high level of academic performance based on the rating presented in the table. This means that the learners generally performed excellently in their academic work. The result suggests that the respondents may have shown strong mastery of lessons, satisfactory completion of learning tasks, active class participation, and favorable achievement in Social Studies. This implies that the teaching strategies used in Social Studies may have contributed positively to the learners' academic performance. Since the respondents' performance was rated outstanding, Social Studies teachers may continue using varied strategies such as lecture discussion, cooperative learning, technology and multimedia resources, and role playing to sustain learners' interest, participation, and achievement. However, continuous monitoring and intervention programs are still needed to support learners who may have difficulty maintaining this level of performance.

The current finding is supported by Darling-Hammond et al. (2020), who emphasized that meaningful and supportive teaching practices help promote students' learning and academic development. Similarly, Tatal and Yazar (2023) found that active learning improves students' academic achievement and learning retention, suggesting that interactive and learner-centered strategies may contribute to better academic outcomes.

3. Is there a significant relationship between the perceived level of teaching strategies in social studies and respondents' level academic performance?

Table 7: Test of relationship between the perceived level of teaching strategies in social studies and respondents' level academic performance.

Variables Correlated	rho-value	p-value	Interpretation
Teaching Strategies in Social Studies and Academic Performance	0.394	<.001	Positive Medium/Moderate Correlation Significant

**Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level*

Table 7 presents the test of relationship between the perceived level of teaching strategies in Social Studies and the respondents' level of academic performance. The result shows a rho-value of 0.394 with a p-value of < .001, which is lower than the 0.05 level of significance. This indicates a significant moderate positive relationship between teaching strategies in Social Studies and academic performance. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the perceived level of teaching strategies in Social Studies and respondents' level of academic performance is rejected. This finding shows that when Social Studies teaching strategies such as lecture-discussion, cooperative learning, technology and multimedia integration, and role playing are practiced more effectively, students also tend to demonstrate higher academic performance. This result is consistent with the study's finding that there was a significant relationship between Social Studies teaching strategies and academic performance, with a correlation coefficient of 0.394 and a p-value of < .001. This means that effective teaching strategies play an important role in improving students' academic achievement in Social Studies. The positive correlation suggests that students learn better when teachers use varied, interactive, learner-centered, and engaging instructional approaches. Although the relationship is not perfect, the result confirms that teaching strategies are meaningfully connected to learners' performance and may help improve their understanding, participation, retention, and achievement in the subject. This implies that Social Studies teachers should continue strengthening their instructional practices by using strategies that encourage active participation, collaboration, critical thinking, and real-life application of lessons. Teachers may further enhance academic performance by improving classroom discussions, organizing cooperative learning activities, integrating multimedia resources, and using role-playing activities to make Social Studies more meaningful and engaging. The result may also serve as a basis for designing an intervention program that focuses on improving instructional delivery, student engagement, collaborative learning, multimedia utilization, and performance-based activities.

The current finding is supported by Tatal and Yazar (2023), who found that active learning improves students' academic achievement and learning retention, showing that learner-centered strategies can positively influence performance. Similarly, Darling-Hammond et al. (2020) emphasized that meaningful, supportive, and well-designed teaching practices help promote students' learning and academic development. The finding is also supported by the reviewed literature in the study, which states that teaching strategies such as lecture-discussion, cooperative learning, technology and multimedia resources, and role playing make Social Studies instruction more interactive, engaging, and meaningful, thereby contributing to better academic outcomes.

DISCUSSION

The findings indicate that Social Studies teachers at Dapitan City National High School employ varied teaching strategies to a full extent, as reflected in the overall mean of 4.38. Among the strategies, role playing obtained the highest rating, followed by cooperative learning, lecture-discussion, and the incorporation of technology and multimedia resources. This suggests that students respond positively to interactive and learner-centered approaches that allow them to participate actively, collaborate with peers, understand historical and social situations, and connect classroom lessons with real-life experiences. The respondents also demonstrated outstanding academic performance, with an average weighted value of 4.54. Moreover, the significant moderate positive relationship between teaching strategies and academic performance ($\rho = 0.394$, $p < .001$) shows that the effective use of varied instructional approaches is associated with higher student achievement. Although other personal and environmental factors may also influence academic outcomes, the result emphasizes the important role of teachers in creating engaging, meaningful, and responsive learning experiences. Therefore, Social Studies teachers should continue strengthening role-playing, cooperative activities, interactive discussions, and technology-supported instruction to sustain students' participation, understanding, and academic success.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that Social Studies teachers at Dapitan City National High School employ lecture-discussion, cooperative learning, technology and multimedia integration, and role-playing strategies to a full extent, with role playing emerging as the most highly perceived approach. The respondents also demonstrated an outstanding level of academic performance. Furthermore, the significant moderate positive relationship between teaching strategies and academic performance indicates that the effective use of varied, interactive, and learner-centered instructional approaches is associated with better student achievement in Social Studies. Therefore, sustaining and further enhancing these teaching strategies, particularly through stronger technology integration and engaging classroom activities, may help improve students' participation, understanding, and academic outcomes.

RECOMMENDATION

It is recommended that Social Studies teachers continue using varied, interactive, and learner-centered strategies, particularly role playing, cooperative learning, and lecture-discussion, while further strengthening the integration of technology and multimedia resources in classroom

instruction. School heads would provide regular instructional supervision, mentoring, and professional development activities focused on digital teaching tools, collaborative learning, and performance-based activities. DepEd officials would also support schools by providing adequate technological resources, relevant learning materials, and training programs that enhance teachers' instructional competence. Parents should encourage consistent study habits at home, while students should actively participate in classroom discussions and group activities. Future researchers would conduct similar studies in other schools or divisions and include additional variables to further examine the factors that influence students' academic performance in Social Studies.

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REFERENCES

- 1) Agustin, S. P., Alvarez, J. I., & Del Carmen, J. M. V. (2025). Mediators of teaching strategies and students' academic performance in social studies: A mediation analysis. *Educational Process: International Journal*, 16, Article e2025207. <https://doi.org/10.22521/edupij.2025.16.207>
- 2) Aiken, L. S., & Susane, G. (2001). *West multiple progression*. Sage Publishing, Inc.
- 3) Al-Mubireek, S. (2021). The effects of cooperative learning versus traditional teaching on students' achievement: A case study. *TESOL International Journal*, 16(5), 168–193.
- 4) Al-Shuqairat, S. R. (2025). The effectiveness of using digital scientific stations in teaching social studies on the development of visual thinking and self-learning skills among seventh-grade students. *Educational Process: International Journal*.
- 5) Altaftazani, D. H., Sapriya, Maftuh, B., & Agustin, M. (2025). Objective conditions of social studies learning in improving students' conflict-resolution skills in elementary schools. *KnE Social Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v10i12.18865>
- 6) Bihag, J. G. Q., Celso, R. B., Arabbi, A. A., Ladjakahal, M. L., Ildana, N. J., Karim, S. N. I., Sahidul, Z. A., Tandih, S. A., & Kunting, A. F. (2025). Instructional practices of social studies teachers in basic education. *Journal of Health Research and Society*, 4(1), 93–106. <https://doi.org/10.34002/jhrs.v4i1.114>
- 7) Boke, H., Araujo, R., Sierra-Díaz, J., Hortigüela-Alcalá, D., & Pérez-Pueyo, Á. (2025). Effects of cooperative learning on students' learning outcomes in physical education: A meta-analysis. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 16, Article 1508808.
- 8) Brown, L. G., & Chidume, T. (2023). Don't forget about role play: An enduring active teaching strategy. *Teaching and Learning in Nursing*, 18(1), 238–241. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.teln.2022.09.002>
- 9) Cai, Z., & Meng, Q. (2025). Academic resilience and academic performance of university students: The mediating role of teacher support. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 16, Article 1463643.
- 10) Check, J., & Schutt, R. K. (2012). *Research methods in education*. SAGE Publications. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781544307725>
- 11) Cohen, J. (1988). *Statistical power analysis for the behavioral sciences* (2nd ed.). Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- 12) Creswell, J. W., & Guetterman, T. C. (2019). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research* (6th ed.). Pearson.
- 13) Darling-Hammond, L., Flook, L., Cook-Harvey, C., Barron, B., & Osher, D. (2020). Implications for educational practice of the science of learning and development. *Applied Developmental Science*, 24(2), 97–140. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10888691.2018.1537791>
- 14) Delgado-Galindo, P., García-Jiménez, J., Torres-Gordillo, J.-J., & Rodríguez-Santero, J. (2025). School climate and academic performance: Key factors for sustainable education in high-efficacy schools and low-efficacy schools. *Sustainability*, 17(14), Article 6497. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17146497>
- 15) Eikeland, I., & Ohna, S. E. (2022). Differentiation in education: A configurative review. *Nordic Journal of Studies in Educational Policy*, 8(3), 157–170. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20020317.2022.2039351>
- 16) Gillies, R. M. (2016). Cooperative learning: Review of research and practice. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 41(3), 39–54. <https://doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2016v41n3.3>
- 17) Gyeltshen, L. (2021). Enhancing sixth-grade students' learning in social studies through technology-based approaches. *Bhutan Journal of Research and Development*.
- 18) Hafeez, M. (2021). Impact of teachers' training on the interest and academic achievement of students through multiple teaching methods. *Pedagogical Research*, 6(3). <https://doi.org/10.29333/pr/11187>
- 19) Haleem, A., Javaid, M., Qadri, M. A., & Suman, R. (2022). Understanding the role of digital technologies in education: A review. *Sustainable Operations and Computers*, 3, 275–285. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.susoc.2022.05.004>
- 20) Ituralde, A. J., & Garcia, L. H. (2025). Influencing factors of students' preference toward specialization selection among Grade 9 students. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, 6(8), 5590–5604.
- 21) Jibililu, O. S. (2024). Evaluating the impact of instructional materials on social studies learning outcomes in senior high schools in the Bono East Region of Ghana. *Social Education Research*, 5(2), 380–397. <https://doi.org/10.37256/ser.5220244881>
- 22) Kara, S., & Tekindur, M. (2025). The effect of differentiated instruction on the academic achievement and opinions of third-grade students in science education: A mixed- methods study. *Journal of Intelligence*, 13(10), Article 126. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jintelligence13100126>

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- 23) Kyei, S., & Tedukpor, J. (2025). Teaching Social Studies in high schools: Knowledge construction versus knowledge transmission methods. *EIKI Journal of Effective Teaching Methods*, 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.59652/jetm.v3i1.355>
- 24) Lamaro, G., & Anena, D. J. (2024). Relationship between teaching strategies and students' academic performance at ordinary-level secondary schools in Gulu District. *East African Journal of Education Studies*, 7(2), 330–347. <https://doi.org/10.37284/eajes.7.2.1953>
- 25) Löfstrand, P., Zakrisson, I., Cehajic-Clancy, S., & Jonsson, R. (2025). Exploring the impact of role-playing exercises on cognitive and emotional engagement with complex social phenomena. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 16, Article 1645213.
- 26) Manan, & Mastul, A. R. H. (2023). The impact of applying the role-playing method on social studies lessons among fourth-grade students. *Journal of Pedagogy and Education Science*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.56741/jpes.v2i01.99>
- 27) Mellado-Moreno, P. C., & Burgos, C. (2025). Didactics in social studies for global citizenship education: Dimensions and technological contexts. *Frontiers in Education*, 10, Article 1514027. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2025.1514027>
- 28) Nguyen, T. N. T., & Oanh, D. T. K. (2025). Cooperative learning and its influences on student engagement. *Cogent Education*, 12(1), Article 2513414.
- 29) Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. (2021). *The state of school education: One year into the COVID pandemic*. OECD Publishing.
- 30) Qin, Z., Chen, Y., & Liu, Z. (2025). The impact of academic burnout on academic achievement: A moderated chain mediation effect from the stimulus-organism-response perspective. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 16, Article 1559330.
- 31) Rashid, S., & Qaisar, S. (2017). Role play: A productive teaching strategy to promote critical thinking. *Bulletin of Education and Research*, 39(2), 197–213.
- 32) Reardon, S. F. (2019). Educational opportunity in early and middle childhood: Using full-population administrative data to study variation by place and age. *RSF: The Russell Sage Foundation Journal of the Social Sciences*, 5(2), 40–68. <https://doi.org/10.7758/RSF.2019.5.2.03>
- 33) Refugio, C. N., Galleto, P. G., & Torres, R. (2019). Competence landscape of Grade 9 mathematics teachers: Basis for an enhancement program. *Cypriot Journal of Educational Sciences*, 14(2), 241–256. <https://doi.org/10.18844/cjes.v14i2.4125>
- 34) Rožman, M., Vrečko, I., & Tominc, P. (2025). Psychological factors impacting academic performance among business studies students. *Education Sciences*, 15(2), Article 121. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci15020121>
- 35) Segura Hudson, M. (2025). More than a game: Strengthening subject literacy through role-play in a content and language integrated classroom. *Frontiers in Education*, 10, Article 1685102.
- 36) Shih, Y.-H. (2024). Children's learning for sustainability in social studies: A study of story-based teaching. *Frontiers in Education*, 9, Article 1353420. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2024.1353420>
- 37) Schmid, R., Pauli, C., & Petko, D. (2023). Examining the use of digital technology in schools with a school-wide approach to personalized learning. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 71(2), 367–390. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-022-10167-z>
- 38) Tatoy, E. V. (2025). High school students' learning-style preferences and level of academic achievement: A cross-sectional study. *European Online Journal of Natural and Social Sciences*, 14(3), 181–194.
- 39) Tomlinson, C. A. (2017). *How to differentiate instruction in academically diverse classrooms* (3rd ed.). ASCD.
- 40) Tatal, Ö., & Yazar, T. (2023). Active learning improves academic achievement and learning retention in K–12 settings: A meta-analysis. *SAGE Open*, 13(2). <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440231177077>
- 41) United Nations Children's Fund. (2017). *The adolescent brain: A second window of opportunity—A compendium*. UNICEF Office of Research–Innocenti.
- 42) United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. (2019). *From access to empowerment: UNESCO strategy for gender equality in and through education 2019–2025*. UNESCO.
- 43) Valente, S., Lourenço, A. A., & Németh, Z. (2020). School conflicts: Causes and management strategies in classroom relationships. In M. P. Levine (Ed.), *Interpersonal relationships*. IntechOpen. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.95395>
- 44) Wang, H., Zhang, T., & Li, Y. (2024). The effects of cooperative learning approaches on students' interpersonal competence: A systematic review. *Current Psychology*.
- 45) Yalçın, A., & Güleç, S. (2024). Activity-based social studies teaching: An investigation of activity-based teaching of responsibility as a value. *Journal of Inquiry Based Activities*, 14(1), 43–61.
- 46) Zhang, H., Yang, J., & Liu, Y. (2024). Effect of teachers' teaching strategies on students' learning engagement: A moderated mediation model. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 15, Article 1475048. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1475048>